

TRAINING PROGRAMS NEEDED TO DEVELOP YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS FROM TRAINING INSTITUTIONS IN BANDUNG: A QUALITATIVE PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Unemployment is a problem that is often faced by every country, especially developing countries like Indonesia. The high level of unemployment in a country can have a negative impact on the economy of a country. Entrepreneurship is the potential to build the economy for the better. Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung is one of the training institutions that can develop entrepreneurial potential. This study used a qualitative descriptive method. Researchers found that in organizing training for young entrepreneurs, one of the training evaluation techniques was adopted, namely IPOO. In terms of Input regarding the recruitment of training participants, the Process in this program aims to become more independent and free from dependence. The Output and Outcomes of the training participants are motivated to start a business and make it easier for them to manage themselves better.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Duta Transformasi Insani, IPOO, Qualitative Research

1. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment is an employment problem that every country, especially developing countries like Indonesia, often faces. The unemployment problem has always been a problem that needs to be solved in the Indonesian economy. The population growth every year has brought about an increase in the number of laborers. A country's high unemployment rate may harm a country's economy. Unemployment occurs because the growth of the labor force is higher than the growth of existing jobs. Unemployment is one of the crucial indicators in the employment field, where the unemployment rate can measure the extent to which existing employment opportunities can absorb labor. High unemployment rates may be the primary source of poverty, leading to high crime rates and long-term

impediments to development (Artiyan, 2003).

Economic development is an effort to provide life skills to the broader community, especially youth, to improve their future. Development leads to changes for the better than the previous standard of living. Development in the era of globalization relies heavily on the economic sector as a measure of the progress of a nation (Sarfiyah, Atmaji, & Verawati, 2019)

Efforts to support economic development and the need for entrepreneurial development, especially in youth through training activities, must intensify. As a form of effort that can be done is to hold training to form strong entrepreneurs. The low interest in entrepreneurship for young people starts from the lack of support from parents and the lack of attention from formal education institutions (Sunarmintyastuti et al., 2021)

Entrepreneurship training aims to develop youth interest and motivation to enter the world of entrepreneurship, develop knowledge and skills in business governance development, marketing production, and business networks, and develop young entrepreneurs' skills in entrepreneurial development efforts among youth (Sunarmintyastuti et al., 2021)

With the holding of entrepreneurial training that can provide financial and non-financial benefits, the form of financial benefits obtained is economic independence in running a business, while from a non-financial perspective in the form of solid and unyielding mental growth in facing life's problems (Rahyono, & Alansori, 2021)

Entrepreneurship training is one of the most important things to build and develop the Indonesian economy. One of the fundamental problems that have become the biggest challenge for the Indonesian nation is economic development. This economic development will provide growth and prosperity for the citizens of a nation. In this case, the problem faced by the Indonesian nation is that the increase in human resources causes more unemployment.

The view of the people who rely more on diplomas than to explore their potential is considered the cause of economic development obstruction in society. Therefore, to develop the Indonesian economy, the role of entrepreneurs will be increasingly felt because development will be more successful if successful entrepreneurs in their business support it.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Young Entrepreneurship Training

Entrepreneurship is development potential, both in number and in the quality of entrepreneurship itself. In the increasingly rapid globalization flow, we are challenged

not only to prepare human resources (HR) who are ready to work but also to prepare and open new jobs. Opening and expanding new job opportunities is a very urgent need. Entrepreneurship is a mental attitude and spirit that is always active or creative power, understated, and trying to increase revenue in its business activity (Amin, 2008).

Besides, entrepreneurship is an attitude and enthusiasm that is always active or creative, work, and uncertain business to increase income in business activities (Duanamu, 2013). Moreover, entrepreneurship is an attitude, passion, and struggle for an economic system because the classic aspect of entrepreneurship education programs is training about the business plan itself (Fregetto, 2005).

(Nagel, 2016) states that entrepreneurship is the ability possessed by a person to see and assess business opportunities, gather the resources needed to take appropriate action, and take advantage in order to achieve success. Because of that, of course, it takes the role of youth who are quite creative in doing business. Such as the statement (Syaifullah, 2009) states that qualitatively youth have pure, innovative, and creative idealism. This is a strategic element that youth is an incredible energy in changing a nation.

The reasons for the need for entrepreneurs to encourage economic growth in Indonesia include: 1) With entrepreneurship, people can have the ability to create their original creative results so that the state does not need to import when the community can make products that are useful for many people, 2) society becomes more independent because an entrepreneur will bring turnover that will be given to the state through taxes which make the community's economy stable, 3) attract foreign investors to invest in Indonesia, when there are foreign investors it will be able to increase the country's foreign exchange (Sulistiono, Nurendah, & Mulyana, 2019)

Higher education plays a role in encouraging graduates to become entrepreneurs. There will be a cycle of increasing entrepreneurship from undergraduate circles, which will reduce the number of unemployed and increase employment (Sulistiono, Nurendah, & Mulyana, 2019). To open up new jobs, entrepreneurship training is needed for several components of society. Entrepreneurship training will not run well without management because human abilities are limited (physical, knowledge, time, and training) while their needs are unlimited.

The influence of entrepreneurship education has been considered as one of the critical factors for fostering and developing entrepreneurial interest, spirit, and behavior among the younger generation (Indarti, & Rostiani, 2008). The reason is that a business plan is a necessity for every entrepreneur. Business plans should be beneficial for entrepreneurs, but most entrepreneurs do not prepare them, even though business plans are generally assumed to lead to success in entrepreneurship. Because with the concept of entrepreneurship, several systems will be encouraged to be more advanced such as economic growth, technological innovation, job creation, and increased employment in most countries (Stamboulis & Barlas, 2014)

To access social capital and turn it into economic capital, of course, requires entrepreneurial literacy and not only the trust that needs to be given to young entrepreneurs. However, the community goal of the organizations they form ensures that people continue to participate and provide access to capital (Johnstone & Lionais, 2006). Because society must make full use of conventional business infrastructure, knowledge, expertise, and networks, do not become a social entrepreneur who does not take advantage of conventional business infrastructure (Leeming, 2002).

Problems with poor planning and implementation and corruption are often

significant problems in entrepreneurial success. Thus, it is essential to consider the cultural environment of entrepreneurs to design suitable entrepreneurial interventions by governments or bilateral and multilateral organizations (Jhosua, & Catherine, 2016). Indeed, there may be differences between young entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs who are already professionals. Differences in social status between young and professional entrepreneurs often imply differences in economic, social, and business opportunities. However, it cannot be separated from that the role of young entrepreneurs is very much needed. Thus, prosperity for the long term certainly requires the participation of young entrepreneurs (Reynolds & Camp, 2000).

This is because young entrepreneurs can make significant contributions to job creation and wealth innovation in all sectors of the economy (Brush et al., 2006). Some young entrepreneurs in developed countries start doing business from the motivation of opportunity and are inversely proportional to youth in developing countries whose economies are less developed because they are motivated by need. Of course, this is different from some of the previous programs, where entrepreneurship programs positively affect the overall intention of entrepreneurship (Maresch et al., 2016) (Souitaris et al., 2007). So entrepreneurs must know the advantages and disadvantages of having control over someone's business, and of course, they must commit to being successful (Pauric et al., 2012).

As internal and external factors for the success of entrepreneurs who do not have formal education confirm that the informal sector is income-generating but creates jobs for the low-skilled and uneducated (Miriam et al., 2012). It can be started from being a small businessman, which of course requires skills and hard work. That is because of own boss and who runs the business (Neely, 2003). Likewise, young entrepreneurs have educational experience, work experience, and business skills. They will mobilize

micro-businesses to larger companies which, of course, all also depend on capital, networks, and innovation (Spring, 2009).

As the expression (Jardon, & Martos, 2012) states, intellectual property can increase the ability of young entrepreneurs to compete in small and large business groups. Because in the era of globalization, competitiveness in the economic sector will be increasingly solitary. The statement (Soltani et al., 2014) suggests that competitive advantage can be realized by developing new products. The product development itself is manifested by the existence of intellectual property owned by the company. Of course, all of this is inseparable from the importance of the entrepreneurial process. In line with the explanation (Nmadu, 2011) also states the importance of entrepreneurial literacy for the younger generation to boost the community's economy. As he said: "It is necessary to expand the literacy of entrepreneurs, especially the establishment of many entrepreneurial centers. To reach this stage, knowledge in the economic sector is undoubtedly necessary to reach the stage of success. In fact (White et al., 2012) show that understanding literacy in entrepreneurship is certainly very supportive of the success of young entrepreneurs.

As the young entrepreneur training at Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung, which is currently known as a young entrepreneurial training institute, has become a new inspiration for the community among youth. This institution focuses on training for young entrepreneurs, and of course, they have thought about inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes (IPOO). Of course, the purpose of this institution is to increase the creativity of young entrepreneurs. This system was formed because many young entrepreneurs who are still low in entrepreneurial literacy only participate independently and focus on individual aspects of entrepreneurship (Ludvik, & Dana, 2017), causing success to

largely depend on the relationship where they are entrepreneurial (Hanson, 2009).

Thus, many young entrepreneurs have focused on learning similar to what entrepreneurs have learned in general (Jennifer & Candida, 2013). It seems clear that entrepreneurial literacy associated with entrepreneurship has not been fully understood and practiced in business activities to create unique values for competitiveness (Martos, 2012). As in the field, there is already a young entrepreneurial training institute at Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung. Several community organizations understand that they need creativity training for the community. These systems have a goal for the younger generation to be more creative, creative, and innovative.

So with the existence of management will form an effort to meet the needs and limited ability to carry out work and encourage people to divide work, duties, and responsibilities. Then, an organization is formed that can complete and ease the work (Hasibuan, 2009). Seeing the current reality, it cannot be denied that the global economic movement is increasingly felt so that it is necessary to build competent and ready to compete for human resources.

Therefore, the need for entrepreneurship training cannot be postponed or neglected again. To implement entrepreneurship training as intended, one of the educational institutions/ institutions that can assist in building and developing entrepreneurial activities is the Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung.

2.2. Entrepreneurship

Previously, Wijaya (2007) stated that being an entrepreneur is not an attractive career choice due to the uncertainty of the situation and the many challenges that will be faced to build a new business. Entrepreneurial problems regarding access to capital, access to finance, access to marketing, access to information and

government policies, and distrust are often the main problems. Even Subroto (2013) also revealed that entrepreneurship is an attitude, passion, and ability to create something new that is valuable and useful for themselves and others.

In addition, Amin (2008) revealed that entrepreneurship is a mental attitude and soul that is always active or creative, empowered, creative, initiative, humble, and trying to increase income in its business activities. Similarly, Duanmu (2013) states that entrepreneurship is an attitude and spirit that is always active or creative, work, and an uncertain business to increase income in its business activities. Likewise, Fregetto (2005) said entrepreneurship is an attitude, passion, and struggle for an economic system because the classic aspect of the entrepreneurship education program is training on the business plan itself.

Nagel also (2016) states that entrepreneurship is the ability possessed by a person to see and assess business opportunities, gather the resources needed to take appropriate action, and take advantage to achieve success. Because of that, of course, it takes the role of youth who are quite creative in business. Syaifullah (2009) stated that qualitatively youth have pure, innovative, and creative ideas. This is a strategic element that youth is an incredible energy in changing a nation.

2.3. Problems Young Entrepreneurship

Problems with poor planning and implementation and corruption are often the main problems in successful entrepreneurship. Thus, it is essential to consider the cultural environment of entrepreneurs to design suitable entrepreneurial interventions by governments or bilateral and multilateral organizations (Jhosua A, O and Abiola Catherine, 2016). Indeed, there may be differences between young entrepreneurs and professional entrepreneurs. Differences in social status

between young and professional entrepreneurs often imply differences in economic, social, and business opportunities. However, it cannot be separated from that the role of young entrepreneurs is needed. Thus, long-term prosperity certainly requires the participation of young entrepreneurs (Reynolds, Hay, & Camp, 2000). Of course, their participation will make the environment not create obstacles to their business development which is dominated by observing some cultural practices that limit their growth (Abimbola et al., 2011).

This is because young entrepreneurs can contribute to innovation in job creation and wealth creation in all sectors of the economy (Brush et al., 2006). Like some young entrepreneurs in developed countries who start their business from the motivation of opportunity and in contrast to the youth of developing countries whose economies are less developed because they are motivated by needs. Of course, this is different from some previous programs, where entrepreneurship programs positively affect overall entrepreneurial intentions (Maresch et al., 2016; Souitaris, Zerbinati, & Al-Laham, 2007). So entrepreneurs must know the advantages and disadvantages of having control over one's business and, of course, must commit to being successful (Pauric M, Caroline L. R, Sarah Y. C & Kate G, 2012).

As internal and external factors, the success of entrepreneurs who do not have formal education confirms that the informal sector is income-generating and creates jobs for the low-skilled and uneducated (Miriam O, Germaine I, Joan F & James L. D, 2012). It can be started from being a small businessman who also requires skill and hard work. This is because the one who is your boss and who runs the business is also you (Glenda S. Neely, 2003). Likewise, young entrepreneurs have educational experience, work experience, and business skills. They will mobilize micro-enterprises to larger companies that depend on capital, networks, and innovation (Anita Spring, 2009).

Jardon and Martos (2012) stated that intellectual property could increase the ability of young entrepreneurs to thrive in small and large business groups. Because in the era of globalization, competitiveness in the economic sector will be increasingly difficult. Soltani et al. (2014) stated that competitive advantage could be realized by developing new products. The product development itself is realized by the existence of intellectual property owned by the company. It all indeed can not be separated from the importance of the entrepreneurial process. In line with the explanation, Nmadu (2011) also suggests the importance of entrepreneurial literacy for the younger generation to encourage the community's economy. As his statement: "There is a need to scale up entrepreneurship literacy, especially putting up many entrepreneurship centers." To reach this stage, it is necessary to know the economic sector to reach the stage of success. Even White et al. (2012) show that an understanding of literacy in entrepreneurship is certainly very supportive of the success of young entrepreneurs.

The youth entrepreneurship training at Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung, which is currently known as a young entrepreneur training institution, has become a new inspiration for youth. This institution focuses on training for young entrepreneurs, and of course, they have thought about the inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes (IPOO). Of course, the purpose of establishing this institution is to increase the creativity of prospective young entrepreneurs. This system was formed because many young entrepreneurs still understand entrepreneurship and participate (Michal, M. Ludvik, E & Dana E 2017). In other words, it can lead to success very much depends on the relationship in which they are. Entrepreneurs (Hanson, 2009). Thus, many young entrepreneurs have focused on learning similar to what entrepreneurs, in

general, have learned (Jennifer E. J & Candida GS, 2013).

It is clear that entrepreneurial literacy related to entrepreneurship has not been fully understood and practiced in business activities to create unique value for competitiveness (Martos 2012). As in the field, there is already a young entrepreneurship training institution at the Bandung Human Transformation Ambassador. Several community institutions have understood that creativity training is needed for the community. These systems have a goal for the younger generation to be more creative, creative, and innovative. It is clear that entrepreneurial literacy related to entrepreneurship has not been fully understood and practiced in business activities to create unique value for competitiveness (Martos 2012). As in the field, there is already a young entrepreneurship training institution at the Bandung Human Transformation Ambassador. Several community institutions have understood that creativity training is needed for the community. These systems have a goal for the younger generation to be more creative, creative, and innovative.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Research Design

This research is a field study conducted using the qualitative method. This study discusses the form of the implementation of young entrepreneurial training at Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung in terms of Input, Process, Output, Outcome (IPOO). This research is a research report, namely research on informants through interviews and various indirect sources. In the research entitled "The form of organizing young entrepreneurial training at Duta Transformasi Insani Bandung in terms of Input, Process, Output, Outcome (IPOO)," the subject is the manager of the Young Entrepreneur program, namely Kang Apudian, S.Sos.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Input

To recruit training participants, the process carried out is to disseminate information to alumni participating in the retirement preparation program. Then, the information is disseminated through the Whatsapp group network. In addition, the participants from the flash boarding school alumni group, who have participated in the Human Transformation Ambassadors. At first, the program of young entrepreneurship training was only for alumni who had participated in training activities in the Human Transformation Ambassador program. However, due to many requests from the general public, this activity began to be disseminated more widely with technical socialization through pamphlets and the official website of the training institution. The requirements for participants to take part in the training for young entrepreneurs include the primary age, wherein in this program, the age requirement for training participants is 17-30 years. So, they carry out administrative processes such as filling out forms and collecting other data. For accommodation costs, especially for alumni who have attended training programs at the institution, will be free or free of charge. When a new person joins the training program, the initial registration fee is an investment fee charged for social activities and activities. -The next activity at the Human Transformation Ambassador. However, the requirements or qualifications of participants are more emphasized from the aspect based on age. In addition, participants who are not in school can also participate, as long as the proposed age requirements can be met. If participants are found who do not meet the qualifications but want to participate in training activities, they are still given the opportunity. However, it is only limited to implementing or assisting training activities for participants who have

businesses. Therefore, participants who do not meet these qualifications will be involved as marketing personnel in the business activities carried out. This is done where the purpose of this training is to form a strong mentality as an entrepreneur. Of course, it must be owned by entrepreneurs. Participants who are at least 17 years old are seen as able to prepare themselves and mentally compared to children under 17 years old.

For instructors of young entrepreneur training, the style conveyed in delivering the material is not in the form of mentoring but more like training delivered in general. Besides that, the particular competencies determined by the institution for instructors include experts in this field of entrepreneurship, and most of them are experts in entrepreneurship. The instructors or presenters are practitioners who are directly involved in the business world. The advantage is that they also understand the theory or concept to be conveyed to the trainees in addition to being an entrepreneur practitioner.

The young entrepreneur program does not have a particular curriculum or training module about the availability of materials. However, the institution only determines what material it wants to convey with the aim that participants can apply the material to be conveyed. Following the institution's objectives, the material presented may change from year to year. This is because the material is based on needs by looking at the current conditions that are considered relevant to the training participants. Facilities obtained by participants during the activity include nametags, seminar kits, pins, and lodging. In implementing the training, the minimum standards are determined by the institution so that participants are comfortable and focused in participating in the training activities.

4.2. Process

Regarding the plan, the specific goal to be achieved in this young entrepreneur training program is to make participants a partner (volunteer) of the Human Transformation Ambassador institution. When there is an ongoing program, the participants who have attended the program at the Human Transformation Ambassador will be notified. Through the Whatsapp group, they will be involved in the program that will be run, be a presenter, and an instructor/facilitator or EO. Determination of program objectives before implementation is to adjust to participants' needs to understand how to find and develop their potential. Participants have the understanding and knowledge of how to build and improve their entrepreneurial competencies. Build motivation and awareness to change themselves from dependence to independence. Participants can understand how to start and manage a profitable business, and participants can find out various alternative business fields that may be developed. The determination of the vision and mission of the young entrepreneur program is by the vision and mission of the institution in general, namely to become a trusted consultant based on heart management, while its mission is to build a nation with excellent and robust character.

Designing training programs before implementation by holding discussions between corporations as program owners since the retirement preparation period (MPP). During the discussion, the corporation delivered the MPP program curriculum. Where participants from retirees are trained so that when they enter retirement, they can be more productive. However, parents who are about to retire are mostly their children who are not ready, and this is because when their parents are still working, all the facilities are still available later on. Retirement, this condition demands from dependence to be independent. The young entrepreneur program was born, which prepares for retirement both from

parents and children; parents must be independent and their children.

In the training model, the manager said it was more of a training model like training in general, and there was a question and answer discussion that was not guided by the 4-step Kirkpatrick training model or other. The evaluation form was applied like an evaluation sheet given to training participants to fill out. Furthermore, give back to the committee, which is good input and advice for the managers and institutions of Transformasi Ambassadors in general. This is also not guided by evaluation models such as CIPP, IPO, etc.

After participating in the program from young entrepreneurs, of course, the trainees' knowledge grew from not knowing to know, such as those who did not know about entrepreneurship to know about the world of entrepreneurship itself, as well as those who needed guidance in getting started. A business will be given, and when they have participated in the program. In this young entrepreneur training, the participants' attitude can undoubtedly become more positive and productive, from initially depending on being more independent and creative, for example, the Martabak Jendral business, which is a tangible result of the product of the Retirement Preparation Period. (MPP) and young entrepreneurs.

The training objectives carried out the program. Some of the participants' minds began to open to not burden their parents in the sense of being more independent in their lives and then enthusiastic about participating in the training. It was seen that some of the training participants came from outside Bandung, and some even came from Medan, Yogyakarta, and around West Java.

4.3. Output

The training participants received material on entrepreneurial motivation. The participants were motivated to start a business that was considered suitable for

them to be carried out and pursued, which was in line with the goals set by this young entrepreneur program. Positive behavior is also reflected in the awareness of personal shortcomings and weaknesses that can be used to develop potential and existing opportunities.

The training participants who participate in the youth entrepreneurship program are greatly helped in their work or business. one of the trainees, after attending the training program, just found out what was lacking or needed to be improved from the business. This also impacts increasing economic students who have been in the business world for a long time.

4.4. Outcome

The training program organized makes it easier for the participants to manage themselves to be more independent and easy to socialize with the surrounding environment and improve the trainees' economy for those who have had a business and have been in it for a long time. Likewise, in terms of productivity, it is easy for participants to improve their abilities after participating in a series of Young Entrepreneur activities. The material presented here is the material that discusses psychologists. In this case, participants are encouraged to compete in the business world from the manager to prepare material regarding the steps taken and the risks when a business is planned to be carried out, of course when participants are mentally ready and develop all their potential. They will be able to create a business to build a business. Himself and open up job opportunities for others, this is proof that when all self-potential is maximized, whatever is planned will run well by the desired expectations.

4.5. Discussion

The productive age population is the population in the age group 15-64 years. The productive age population is considered as

part of the population that participates in ongoing employment activities and has the productive capacity to carry out regional and national development activities (Salsabila, 2020) in entrepreneurship training at the Human Transformation Ambassador institution. The age required for training participants is 17 -30 years old, a very productive age to take part in the training.

The administration is essential in the implementation of education and training because the various components are interconnected. The administration will guide and coordinate all parts to make it a unit. Every Training Instructor and education staff must understand the importance of education management and apply it in their duties and work (Ukur, 2020). The administrative process in organizing this training starts from filling out forms and collecting other data. For accommodation costs, especially for alumni who have attended training programs at the institution, will be free or free of charge. When a participant is found who does not meet the qualifications of the participant but wants to take part in the training activity, the attitude of the institution is that it still provides opportunities for the participant to take part in the activity, but is only limited to an executor or helping from training activities, for example, for example when the training participants If you have a business, then participants who do not meet these qualifications will be involved as marketing or assisting in the business activities carried out, this is done because one of the goals of this training program is to form a mentality that must be strong as an entrepreneur. Of course, it must be owned by entrepreneurs. Participants who are at least 17 years old are seen as able to prepare themselves and mentally compared to children under 17 years old.

Besides that, a special section manages finances in each program, known as ADKE (Financial Administration), both in the Young entrepreneur program, Sanlat, and

other programs. One person is dedicated to taking care of finances in the program. Then in the implementation of the program, there is a kind of budget plan for each program. The general description is, for example, the general participant's accommodation fee is Rp. 1000.000,-, then the money comes from Alumni donors who are already included in the program budget. The maximum budget limit spent in implementing the program adjusts to the number of participants registered in training activities because 25% of the general participant accommodation costs go to the institution, and 75% is used for the needs of the participants during the training activities.

Skills education or entrepreneurial skills training is seen as very effective in helping to solve various problems that surround Indonesian society, including the high unemployment rate caused by unskilled workers. One of the essential steps to create an educated society is the implementation of skills training programs, whose missions are: 1) eliminating unemployment and poverty in urban/rural areas, 2) empowering rural/urban communities 3) optimizing potential and existing job opportunities 4) and improving welfare the community through skills training activities so that they can work or start their own business independently (Saraswati, 2020), in the process of organizing training at the Bandung Human Transformation Ambassador, it aims to reduce unemployment and increase creativity so that they can compete to become entrepreneurs who can take advantage of the potential that exists. is in him.

The output of the training is a measurement of changes in attitudes, knowledge, and skills obtained by training participants through testing and performance evaluation after attending the training. Evaluation of training results can be done at the end of each course material or the end of the training. The outcome of training is an effort to measure changes in attitudes, knowledge, and skills of participants after

training (Widoyoko, 2017). young entrepreneur training participants Obtain material on entrepreneurial motivation. So that participants have the motivation to change their attitudes to become more productive by increasing their knowledge and skills. The results obtained can support the survival of the benchmark for the success that has been planned and executed.

5. CONCLUSION

In implementing the young entrepreneurial training program, some stages have been planned to start from careful planning before implementing activities guided by the concept of IPOO (Input, Process, Output, Outcome). In connection with the concept of Input, it is concluded that the recruitment system is more beneficial to technology for the socialization process to be considered more effective and efficient. The requirements proposed for participants to participate in this activity are the most important in terms of age, namely 17-30 years, instructors who are trusted in The implementation of training for young entrepreneurs is a person who has competence in their field and is a practitioner in the world of entrepreneurship. The material presented is also very relevant to the current conditions conveyed in the form of training. For the facilities obtained by the participants, such as in general, training activity, and from a financial perspective, a particular person was deliberately appointed who was given full responsibility in financial matters called ADKE (Financial Administration). In terms of process, the expected goal with implementing this training is that all participants will be involved in the Duta Transformasi Insani, who can later join to become Volunteers. The design in this program involves discussions between corporate parties and program managers to produce a form of training program design. The output in this program concluded that the training

participants were motivated to start a business and were assisted in the business that was being developed to impact the increase in the economy of the participants. Likewise, in terms of outcomes, it makes it easier for participants to manage themselves to be more independent and easier to socialize to support the progress of the business that is being carried out.

In the future, suggestions or input are given to the Duta Transformasi Insani

training institute. It is necessary to actively involve academics in order to be able to support each series of activities, existing programs, and evaluations of the training held. The hope is that the training institutions can be better and organized by using methods that have been implemented—initiated by scientists and from a series of existing theories.

REFERENCE

- Amin. (2008). Kewirausahaan.<http://viewcomputer.com/kewirausahaan-kangamin>. Diakses pada 12 Januari 2019.
- Candida, B., G & Sarah, C., Y. 2016. Female entrepreneurship and economic development: An international Perspective, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*: Taylor & Francis Group. DOI: 10.1080/08985626.2012.637340 Vol. 24, Nos. 1–2
- Chirikova E A & Babaeva V L, 2016. Women in Business, *Russian Social Science Review*, Taylor & Francis Group. Doi.org/10.2753/RSS1061-1428380381 38:3, 81-91, Vol 36, No 1.
- Duanmu, Jing-Lin & Yilmaz, G. (2013). Heterogeneous effect of ethnic network on International trade of Thailand: The role of family ties and ethnic diversity. *International Business Review*, 22 (1),126-139.
- Fregetto, E. (January 2005). Business plan or business simulation for entrepreneurship education? 19th Annual National Conference Proceedings for the United States Association for Small Business and Entrepreneurship, Indian Wells CA.
- Hanson, S., 2009. Changing places through women's entrepreneurship. *Economic Geography*, Vol. 85, 245–267.
- Harvey Johnstone & Doug Lionais. 2006. Depleted communities and community business entrepreneurship: revaluating space through place, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development* : Taylor & Francis Group, DOI: 10.1080/0898562042000197117, ISSN 0898–5626
- Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. 2009. *Manajemen : Dasar, pengertian, dan Masalah*. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara
- Indarti, N., & Rostiani, R. (2008). Entrepreneurial intention among students: A comparison among Indonesia, Japan, Norway. *Jurnal Ekonomika dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 23 (4), 369-384.
- Jardon, C., M and Martos M.,S. 2012. Intellectual capital as competitive advantage in emerging clusters in Latin America *Journal of Intellectual Capital* Vol. 13 No. 4, 2012 pp. 462-48
- Jennifer, E., J & Candida, G., S. 2013. Research on Women Entrepreneurs: Challenges to (and from) the Broader Entrepreneurship Literature?, *The Academy of Management Annals* : Taylor & Francis Group, Doi : org/10.1080/19416520.2013.782190, Vol. 7, No. 1.
- Jhosua, A., O & Abiola Catherine. 2016. Qualitative exploration of cultural practices inhibiting rural women entrepreneurship development in selected communities in

- Nigeria, *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*: Taylor & Francis Group. Doi: org/10.1080/0827 6331.2015.1102476, Vol. 28, No. 2.
- Kasmir. 2007. *Kewirausahaan*. Jakarta : PT.Raja Grafindo
- Lies Sunamintyastuti, H,A,Prabowo, Dwi Narsih, H,A,Suprpto, D,M, Vernia (2021). Peran pelatihan kewirausahaan dan minat siswa Yayasan Tahfidzul Ar-Rahmani Tangerang Selatan. *JIWP Vol.7, No.2/April 2021*
- Maresch, D. Harms, R., Kailer, N. & Wimmer-Wurm B. (2016). The impact of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention of students in science and engineering versus business studies university programs. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 104, 172– 179.
- Miriam, O. Germaine, I. Joan, F. & James, L., D. 2012. *Micro Entrepreneurship in Niger: Factors Affecting the Success of Women Street Food Vendors*, *Journal of African Business*: Taylor & Francis Group, DOI: 10.1080/15228916.2012.657937, ISSN:1522-8916, 13(1), 16–28.
- Nagel, P. Julius F. 2016. *Pengembangan Jiwa dan Kecerdasan Wirausaha untuk Kemandirian Bangsa*. Seminar Nasional IENACO ISSN: 2337 – 4349.
- Nmadu.,T.,W (2011). *Enhancing Women’s Participation in Formal and Informal Sectors of Nigeria’s Economy Through Entrepreneurship Literacy*. *Journal of Business Diversity* vol. 11(1) 87-98
- Pauric, M. Caroline, L. R. Sarah, Y. C. & Kate, G. 2012. *Female entrepreneurship and the management of business and domestic roles: Motivations, expectations and realities*, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development* :Taylor & Francis Group, DOI: 10.1080/0898562 6.2012.637351 Vol. 24, No. 1–2
- Rahyono, Apip Alansori (2021). *Pelatihan kewirausahaan bagi pelaku UMKM dan masyarakat di kelurahan Sukarame Bandar Lampung*. Vol.2,No.1 Februari 2021.
- Salsabila, Jovita (2020). “Analisis Kondisi Usia Produktif Terhadap Strategi Optimalisasi Usia Produktif dalam Menghadapi Bonus Demografi”, *Departemen sains Komunikasi dan pengembangan Masyarakat, Fakultas Ekologi Manusia, IPB*, Vol 9, No 3
- Saraswati, Prihatin (2020) “Pembekalan Pentingnya Mengikuti Pelatihan N Ketrampilan Berbasis Sumber daya Keluarga Dan Masyarakat Untuk Peningkatan Kesejahteraan Keluarga Di Kota Yogyakarta” *Abdimas akademika*, Vol 1 No.01 hal-80-92.
- Soltani et al. 2014. *A Structural Equation Model of the Impact of New Product Development on Competitive Advantage Engineering Management Research*; Vol. 3, No. 1 hlm 99-108
- Subroto, W.T. (2013). *Entrepreneurship development course to foster character merchandise in support economic growth*. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 1 (1), 1-9.
- S,N, Safiah, H,E, Atmaja, D,M, Verawati (2019). *UMKM sebagai pilar membangun ekonomi bangsa*. *Jurnal REP Vol 4/No.1/2019*.
- Sulisiono, Y, Nurendah, M, Mulayana (2019). *Mengukur Minat studi siswa SMK dan SMA di kota Bogor pada program studi kewirausahaan*. *JAS-PT Vol 3/No.1/2019*.
- Syaifullah, Chavchay. 2009. *Generasi Muda Menolak Kemiskinan*. Penerbit Cempaka Putih. Klaten.
- Ukur, Jumba (2020) “ *Manfaat dan kendala administrasi pendidikan dalam penyelenggaraan pendidikan* ” *Jurnal Ilmiah Research Sains Vol.6*.
- Widoyoko, E. P. (2017). *Evaluasi program pelatihan*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar

White, R.J Hertz, G.T, Koutroumanis G.A. 2012. Entrepreneurship Literacy: the Language of the New Venture. Journal of Applied Business and Economics vol. 13(5) hlm 35-45.